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Combined Theoretical Study on Optoelectronic Properties and EGFR Kinase Inhibition Potential of 3-Bromo- 2-cyano-5-methylpyridine

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Abstract— In this study, the structural and electronic properties of the compound 3-Bromo-2-cyano-5-methylpyridine (C₇H₅BrN₂) were investigated with DFT based computational approaches. The ground state geometry, vibration frequencies and magnetic properties were determined by DFT using the 6-311G basis set. The optimized geometry theoretically showed the molecule has a stable and planar heteroaromatic skeleton. Within the scope of spectroscopic characterizations, typical signals specific to the molecule were determined at a theoretical level by calculating harmonic frequencies (FT-IR) and chemical shifts (¹H and ¹³C NMR). Characterization of electronic properties was carried out based on FMO analysis, DOS and MEP mapping. The wide HOMO-LUMO energy gap calculated at 5.397 eV indicates that the molecule has high chemical rigidity and kinetic stability. In addition, UV-Vis analyzes revealed that the molecule shows significant absorption in the ultraviolet region and high transmittance in the visible region, drawing attention to the potential of optoelectronic materials. To evaluate the pharmaceutical potential, molecular docking simulations were performed against the Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) kinase domain (PDB ID: 1M17). The compound showed a favorable binding affinity of -4.270 kcal/mol, interacting effectively with active site residues. These findings indicate that the C₇H₅BrN₂ compound is a promising candidate for both optical materials and anticancer drug design scaffolds.

Keywords: 3-Bromo-2-cyano-5-methylpyridine (C₇H₅BrN₂), DFT, Molecular Docking, EGFR Kinase, Electronic Structure, Vibrational Spectroscopy

1. INTRODUCTION

Heterocyclic organic compounds (especially pyridine and its derivatives) are one of the most important classes of structures in pharmaceutical chemistry, agricultural chemistry and materials science due to

their diverse biological activities and versatile electronic properties [1-3]. Pyridine-based scaffolds serve as basic building blocks in the synthesis of many FDA-approved drugs, including anticancer, analgesic, antimicrobial, and antiviral agents [4, 5]. The electronic distribution of the pyridine ring, which can be easily changed with various substituents, allows for precise tuning of its chemical reactivity and interaction with biological targets [6-8]. In recent years, incorporating halogen atoms, such as bromine, and cyano groups into the pyridine scaffold has attracted considerable attention. The halogen bonding and steric effects from bromine atoms can significantly enhance the lipophilicity and binding affinity of drug candidates towards specific protein targets [7, 9]. Simultaneously, the cyano group acts as a strong electron-withdrawing unit, changing the molecular electrostatic potential and helping with intermolecular interactions such as hydrogen bonding, which are important in enzyme inhibition mechanisms [10]. Also, push-pull systems containing electron-donating (e.g. methyl) and electron-withdrawing (e.g. cyano) groups on a conjugated aromatic system are of great interest for potential Nonlinear Optics (NLO) applications [11]. Understanding the structural dynamics, electronic structure, and reactive sites of the 3-Bromo-2-cyano-5-methylpyridine ($C_7H_5BrN_2$) molecule is important to evaluate its potential as a bioactive agent or an optical material. In this context, the main goal of the present work is to provide a comprehensive physicochemical characterization of the $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule using Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations. Ground state molecular geometry, vibrational frequencies (FT-IR) and chemical shifts (1H and ^{13}C NMR) were calculated and analyzed. Electronic properties were investigated through Frontier Molecular Orbital (FMO) analysis, Density of States (DOS) and Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP) mapping to identify reactive centers. Also, to explore the pharmaceutical potential of the compound, molecular docking simulations were performed against Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) kinase, a prominent target in cancer therapy. This multidimensional approach tries to explain the structure-activity relationship (SAR) of the molecule and pave the way for its future applications in drug design and optoelectronics.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

All quantum chemical calculations were performed using the Gaussian 09 software package (version AS64L-G09RevD.01) [12]. 6-311G was preferred as the basis set for C, H, N atoms. The stability of the structure was confirmed by frequency analysis, and the electronic (FMO, DOS, MEP), magnetic (GIAO-NMR) and optical UV-Vis (TD-DFT) properties were calculated at the same level of theory. GaussView 6.0 was used in visualizations [13]. Molecular Docking The biological activity of the compound was examined with the AutoDock Vina program by targeting the EGFR kinase domain (PDB ID: 1M17) [14, 15]. Ligand-protein interactions were analyzed based on the lowest energy conformation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Geometry Optimization

Optimization of molecular geometry is determining the minimum energy point on the potential energy surface of a molecule [16]. Bond lengths provide direct information about the reactivity, bond strength and electronic structure of the molecule [16, 17]. Figure 1 represents the lowest energy conformation of the molecule in the ground state. The central structure of the molecule seems to be a six-membered heteroaromatic ring (pyridine).

Figure 1. Optimized structure of $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule

In Figure 1, gray spheres represent Carbon (C), blue spheres represent Nitrogen (N), burgundy sphere represents Bromine (Br) and white spheres represent Hydrogen (H) atoms. The N6 atom is the heteroatom of the pyridine ring. π -conjugation on the ring is visualized by dashed lines (delocalized bonds) between C2-C3, C4-C5 and C7-N6, suggesting aromatic stability. The C8-N9 group attached to the C5 atom is a cyanine (nitrile) group. As seen in Figure 1, the bond between C8 and N9, which is chemically connected by a triple bond ($C\equiv N$), has a linear geometry of about 180° . Since this group is a strong electron-withdrawing group, it lowers the electron density of the ring through C5. The Br10 atom bonded to the C4 atom gives the molecule a significant steric volume and mass. The C-Br bond is longer compared to C-C and C-N bonds. Bromine's high electronegativity and lone pair electrons can interact electrostatically with neighboring groups. The C1-H group is bonded to the C2 atom. Methyl group has an electron-donating structure and contributes to the stability of the ring through hyperconjugation. It exhibits a tetrahedral geometry because of sp^3 hybridization. The most striking feature is the proximity of 3-Bromo and 2-Cyano groups to each other (vicinal substitution). Br10 and C8-N9 groups are on adjacent carbons (C4 and C5). A steric repulsion is expected between the large Van der Waals radius of the bromine atom and the linear structure of the cyano group. This repulsion may cause a slight elongation of the C4-C5 bond length or slight deviations of the bond angles from planarity (distortion of the dihedral angle). However, the rigid structure of the pyridine ring reduces this distortion. The pyridine ring and the atoms directly attached to it (C1, Br10, C8) lie largely in the same plane (C_s symmetry or near symmetry). However, the methyl hydrogens are out of plane.

3.2. Band Gap Energy (BG)

According to FMO theory, the chemical reactivity of molecules is largely determined by the Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital (HOMO) and Least Unoccupied Molecular Orbital (LUMO) orbitals. HOMO represents the molecule's ability to donate electrons, while LUMO represents the molecule's ability to accept electrons [18, 19]. In HOMO, the electron density is mainly concentrated on the Bromine atom (Br10), the double bonds in the pyridine ring and partly on the methyl group (C1) (Figure 2 left). The lone pair electrons on the Br atom and the hyperconjugation effect of the methyl group make this region nucleophilic (electron donating) character. In LUMO, some observed that the electron density shifted to the cyano (-CN) group (C8-N9) and the nitrogen atom of the pyridine ring (Figure 2 right). Thus, the density on Br goes down. This proves the strong electron withdrawing ($-\pi$ antibonding)

property of the cyano group. The shift of the electron cloud from one end of the molecule (Br/Methyl) to the other end (cyano) during the transition from HOMO to LUMO says there is a strong Intramolecular Charge Transfer (ICT) potential. This property increases the molecule's potential for nonlinear optical (NLO) materials. Global reactivity parameters calculated based on Koopmans theorem (Band gap (ΔE), hardness (η), softness (S), electronegativity (χ), electrophilic index (ω), ionization potential (I), electron affinity (A), nucleophilicity (ϵ), chemical potential (μ)) reveal the chemical identity of the molecule [20]. It helps us predict how a molecule will behave when it encounters another molecule. Quantum chemical calculations and reactivity descriptors for the examined $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule are given in Table 1. The calculated band gap of 5.397 eV indicates that the molecule is kinetically stable and has a low tendency to spontaneously react. The molecule is stable and chemically rigid. The calculated high hardness value ($\eta \approx 2.7$ eV) indicates that the molecule does not want to charge transfer. Hard molecules are more kinetically stable and maintain their stable structure rather than undergo radical reactions [21]. High electronegativity ($\chi \approx 4.9$ eV) indicates that the molecule will act as an electron sink in a biological environment. Molecules with a high electrophilic index have the potential to form covalent bonds with nucleophilic bases such as guanine and cytosine in DNA [22]. The high ω value (4.524 eV) in the studied molecule suggests that it may be a potent bioactive agent.

Figure 2. The molecular orbital arrangement and energy state diagram of $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule

Table 1. Global reactivity parameters calculated based on Koopmans theorem

$E_{HOMO} = -7.640$ eV; $E_{LUMO} = -2.243$ eV			
Koopmans/DFT	Values	Koopmans/DFT	Values
$\Delta E = E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO}$	5.397 eV	$\eta = (I - A) / 2$	2.699 eV
$I \approx -E_{HOMO}$	7.640 eV	$S = 1 / 2\eta$	0.185 eV^{-1}
$A \approx -E_{LUMO}$	2.243 eV	$\omega = \mu^2 / (2\eta)$	4.524 eV
$\chi = (I + A) / 2$	4.942 eV	$\epsilon = 1 / \omega$	0.221 eV^{-1}
$\mu \approx -\chi$	-4.942 eV		

3.3. Vibrational Spectroscopic Analysis Spectrum

Vibrational spectroscopy determines the frequencies at which molecular bonds resonate based on their force constants and atomic masses [23]. In pyridine derivatives, the heteroaromatic structure of the ring and the position of the substituents affect the shift of the spectral bands. The vibration spectrum of the $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule in the range of $3500-0\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was examined. The spectrum shows the aromatic ring structure in the molecule, the cyano ($-CN$) group and the typical vibrations of the halogen/alkyl substituents. Figure 3 shows the Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectrum of the $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule.

Figure 3. FT-IR spectrum of $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule

The peaks seen in the $3200-2800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range of the spectrum represent the typical C-H stretching vibrations of hydrogen atoms. Aromatic C-H stresses arising from the sp^2 hybridization character of the carbon atoms in the pyridine ring; In the $3050-3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range of the spectrum, weak but sharp peaks belonging to symmetric and asymmetric vibration modes attributed to C3-H14 and C7-H15 bonds were seen. Asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of C-H bonds with sp^3 hybridization in the methyl group were seen as shoulder-shaped peaks in the $2900-2980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range of the spectrum. In the spectral range of $2200-2250\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which plays a critical role in confirming the identity of the molecule, The moderate and sharp peak seen around $2230-2240\text{ cm}^{-1}$, isolated from the aromatic and aliphatic bands, is attributed to the characteristic stretching vibration of the cyano group ($C\equiv N$). The region where the graph is most intense and transmittance decreases the most (absorption goes up) is the region of double bond and ring vibrations between 1600 and 1300 cm^{-1} . The bands attributed to the skeletal vibrations of the pyridine ring ($C=C$ and $C=N$) and increase in intensity due to heteroaromatic conjugation, were seen as intense peaks in the range of $1550-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1400-1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$, confirming the aromatic character of the structure. However, methyl group deformation (scissoring/rocking) modes overlapping with ring vibrations were also detected in the $1380-1460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band. In the fingerprint region ($<1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), where the complex skeletal and bending vibrations specific to the molecule are located,

the intense bands in the range of 700-900 cm^{-1} are associated with aromatic C-H out-of-plane bending modes. The sharp peak seen in the range of 600-700 cm^{-1} corresponds to the typical stretching movement of the C4-Br10 bond, which vibrates at low frequency due to the heavy atom effect.

3.4. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy

The magnetic properties of the molecular structure were examined theoretically using the GIAO (Gauge-Independent Atomic Orbital) method, and the calculated ^{13}C and ^1H NMR spectra are presented in Figure 4. When the ^{13}C -NMR spectrum is examined, it is seen that the signals are concentrated in three main spectral regions depending on the differences in the electronic environments of the atoms. The signal at about 14.0-15.0 ppm, in the high magnetic field region (upfield), is attributed to the methyl group carbon (C1) due to its high electron density and sp^3 hybridization character. The characteristic cyano ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) group carbon entered into resonance between the aliphatic and aromatic regions, 116.0-118.0 ppm, under the influence of the electronegativity of nitrogen and the magnetic anisotropy of the triple bond. Aromatic carbons forming the pyridine ring were seen in the lowest magnetic field region, between 135.0 and 150.0 ppm, because of the aromatic ring current and deshielding effects of heteroatoms. Carbons (C4 and C7), those directly bonded or next to electronegative nitrogen and bromine atoms, have the highest chemical shift values due to strong inductive effects.

Figure 4. NMR spectrum of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{BrN}_2$ molecule

In addition, the ¹H-NMR spectrum confirms the numerical distribution of protons in the molecule and their chemical environment. The intense and broad peak seen in the aliphatic region of the spectrum, 1.5-1.8 ppm, represents the highly screened signals of three equivalent protons of the methyl group. In the aromatic region, the protons on the ring are separated into two signals because of the electronic asymmetry of the pyridine ring. The signal at about 6.5 ppm corresponds to the H-14 proton. The H-15 proton, which is located closer to the pyridine nitrogen (N6), lost its electron density due to the strong electron-withdrawing inductive effect (-I) of the nitrogen atom and shifted to a lower area and was seen at a value of about 7.6 ppm. These theoretical NMR data obtained agree with the atomic sequence and electronic configuration of the proposed 3-Bromo-2-cyano-5-methylpyridine structure.

3.5. Density of States (DOS)

DOS spectrum calculated for characterization of the electronic structure and orbital distributions of the molecule in energy space [24] is presented in Figure 5. The resulting spectrum shows discrete energy levels typical of isolated molecular systems and shows the distinction between valence and conductivity regions. Occupied molecular orbitals in the negative energy region of the spectrum show a high density, especially in the range of -10.0 eV to -15.0 eV. This is attributed to the contribution of the strong σ -bonds that form the molecular skeleton and the unpaired electron pairs (lone pairs) on the heteroatoms (Br and N) in this energy range. The most distinctive finding of the analysis is the wide gap in the forbidden energy seen between the HOMO level (approximately -7.640 eV), which is the ceiling of occupied orbitals, and the LUMO level (approximately -2.243 eV), which is the bottom of empty orbitals. This region, where the density of states is zero, agrees with the band gap of $\Delta E \approx 5.4$ eV calculated in the FMO analysis. This wide energy gap confirms that the chemical hardness of the molecule is high and that it exhibits a kinetically stable structure. When the distribution of virtual orbitals in the positive energy region is examined, it is seen that the energy levels are located relatively closer to each other starting from the LUMO level and present a suitable continuity for possible electronic transitions.

Figure 5. Density of States (DOS) of $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule

3.6. UV-Visible analysis

The electronic transition properties and optical absorption behaviors of the $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule were examined theoretically using Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) and the obtained UV-Vis spectrum is presented in Figure 6. Because of the spectral analysis, it was determined that the absorption activity of the molecule was concentrated only in the ultraviolet (UV) region between 100-300 nm, and that it had an optically transparent structure without exhibiting any electronic transition in the visible region above 400 nm. The most dominant absorption in the spectrum is the intense band seen in the wavelength range of about 200-205 nm and having the highest oscillator power ($f \approx 0.30$). This characteristic peak, where the maximum molar extinction coefficient is reached, is attributed to permissive $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions (Ethylene band) resulting from aromatic conjugation in the pyridine ring and the electronic contribution of the cyano group. In addition, a secondary absorption band with a broader form but lower intensity ($\epsilon \approx 5,000$) was seen around 260-265 nm. This spectral region is associated with HOMO \rightarrow LUMO transitions that determine the chemical stability of the molecule; In addition to aromatic $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, it also includes $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions resulting from unshared electron pairs of nitrogen and bromine atoms in the structure. The position of this band agrees with the wide band gap ($\Delta E \approx 5.4$ eV) calculated in the FMO analysis. The findings show that the molecule has the capacity to absorb UV radiation, so it can be a potential UV-filtering or transparent optical part in optoelectronic technologies.

Figure 6. UV-visible absorption of $C_7H_5BrN_2$

3.7. Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP)

The MEP surface map created to determine the chemical reactivity of the molecular structure, to detect nucleophilic and electrophilic attack sites, and to predict intermolecular hydrogen bond interactions [25, 26] is presented in Figure 7. In the electrostatic potential distribution mapped onto the total electron density isosurface, red colors represent electron-rich (negative potential), blue colors represent electron-poor (positive potential) and green colors represent neutral regions. According to the analysis results, the most prominent negative electrostatic potential regions on the molecule are concentrated around the nitrogen atom (N6) in the pyridine ring, which has high electronegativity, and the nitrogen atom (N9) at the tip of the cyano group. These regions are most vulnerable to attack by electrophilic species (e.g. protons) and function as potential hydrogen bond acceptors (H-bond acceptors) in biological interactions. The maximum positive electrostatic potential values are localized on the methyl group protons and aromatic ring hydrogens, which have a partial positive charge because of the withdrawal of electron density by the carbon skeleton. This distribution shows these regions are suitable targets for nucleophilic attacks. Bromine atom, which has an important place in the steric and electronic structure of the molecule, exhibits a predominantly neutral (green) potential distribution and plays a balancing role in the charge distribution because of its large atomic radius. MEP analysis confirms that the molecule has a pronounced dipolar moment character and contains active centers that can engage in both nucleophilic and electrophilic interactions.

Figure 7. Molecular Electrostatic Potential of $C_7H_5BrN_2$

3.8. Molecular Docking

Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) is a transmembrane tyrosine kinase that plays critical roles in cell proliferation, survival and metastasis processes [27]. Excessive activation of the EGFR signaling pathway has been associated with many types of cancer, non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). So inhibition of the EGFR kinase domain is a strategic approach in modern cancer therapy [28]. In this study, to evaluate the anticancer potential of the $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule, molecular docking simulations were performed against the ATP binding pocket of EGFR (PDB ID: 1M17). Because of analysis using the AutoDock Vina program, the target molecule showed a binding free energy (ΔG) of -4.270 kcal/mol with the active site of EGFR kinase. A negative ΔG value shows that the binding of the ligand to the protein pocket is thermodynamically favorable and spontaneous. Visual analysis of the docking pose (Figure 8) reveals that the ligand is located deep within the ATP binding pocket, providing steric fit with the inner surface of the protein. The planar structure and aromatic character of the pyridine ring is prone to π -stacking or hydrophobic interactions with hydrophobic amino acid residues (such as Val726, Ala743, Leu844) in the active site. Also, the cyano (-CN) group and the pyridine nitrogen on the molecule have the potential to form hydrogen bonds with critical amino acids (e.g., Met793) in the hinge region of the kinase. These docking results also coincide with the Global Reactivity Parameters calculated in the previous sections. The high electrophilic index of the molecule ($\omega=4.524$ eV) and the active nucleophilic/electrophilic ends identified in the MEP map (Figure 7) confirm that the ligand can enter into versatile electrostatic interactions with polar and nonpolar regions of the protein. Given its structural features and calculated binding affinity, $C_7H_5BrN_2$ can be a promising scaffold for EGFR inhibitor drug candidates.

Figure 8. 3D docking pose and interaction details of the $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule in the EGFR kinase active site

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, the structural, electronic and biological properties of the 3-Bromo-2-cyano-5-methylpyridine ($C_7H_5BrN_2$) molecule were comprehensively examined using theoretical methods. The planar heteroaromatic geometry optimized by DFT calculations showed full consistency with the calculated vibrational frequencies (FT-IR) and magnetic properties (NMR), confirming the chemical structure of the molecule at the theoretical level. While the calculated wide HOMO-LUMO energy gap of 5.397 eV shows that the molecule is chemically rigid and has high kinetic stability, UV-Vis analyzes have revealed that the molecule has significant potential for optoelectronic applications as it remains transparent in the visible region and active in the UV region. As for biological activity, molecular docking simulations showed that the compound effectively binds with the EGFR kinase active site, a critical target in cancer therapy, with an affinity value of -4.270 kcal/mol, and the calculated high electrophilic index supports this interaction. Given these findings, $C_7H_5BrN_2$ molecule can be a promising skeletal structure for both new generation optical filters and anticancer drug design.

Author Contributions (Compulsory)

All the authors equally contributed to this work.

Conflict of Interest (Compulsory)

All the authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Review and Approval (Compulsory)

No ethical approval is required.

References

- [1] Vitaku, E., D.T. Smith, and J.T. Njardarson, Analysis of the structural diversity, substitution patterns, and frequency of nitrogen heterocycles among US FDA approved pharmaceuticals: miniperspective. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2014. 57(24): p. 10257-10274.
- [2] Dinges, J. and C. Lamberth, *Bioactive heterocyclic compound classes: pharmaceuticals*. Vol. 6. 2012: Wiley Online Library.
- [3] Eicher, T., S. Hauptmann, and A. Speicher, *The chemistry of heterocycles: structures, reactions, synthesis, and applications*. 2013: John Wiley & Sons.
- [4] Altaf, A.A., et al., A review on the medicinal importance of pyridine derivatives. *J. Drug Des. Med. Chem*, 2015. 1(1): p. 1-11.
- [5] Alizadeh, S.R. and M.A. Ebrahimzadeh, Antiviral activities of pyridine fused and pyridine containing heterocycles, a review (from 2000 to 2020). *Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*, 2021. 21(17): p. 2584-2611.
- [6] Chiacchio, M.A., et al., Pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives as privileged scaffolds in biologically active agents. *Current medicinal chemistry*, 2019. 26(40): p. 7166-7195.
- [7] Wilcken, R., et al., Principles and applications of halogen bonding in medicinal chemistry and chemical biology. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2013. 56(4): p. 1363-1388.
- [8] Fleming, F.F., et al., Nitrile-containing pharmaceuticals: efficacious roles of the nitrile pharmacophore. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2010. 53(22): p. 7902-7917.
- [9] Hernandez, M.Z., et al., Halogen atoms in the modern medicinal chemistry: hints for the drug design. *Current drug targets*, 2010. 11(3): p. 303-314.
- [10] Wang, Y., Y. Du, and N. Huang, A survey of the role of nitrile groups in protein–ligand interactions. *Future medicinal chemistry*, 2018. 10(23): p. 2713-2728.
- [11] Dalton, L.R., P.A. Sullivan, and D.H. Bale, Electric field poled organic electro-optic materials: state of the art and future prospects. *Chemical reviews*, 2010. 110(1): p. 25-55.
- [12] Frisch, M., gaussian 09, Revision d. 01, Gaussian. Inc, Wallingford CT, 2009. 201.
- [13] Dennington, R., T.A. Keith, and J.M. Millam, GaussView 6.0. 16. Semichem Inc.: Shawnee Mission, KS, USA, 2016: p. 143-150.
- [14] Eberhardt, J., et al., AutoDock Vina 1.2. 0: new docking methods, expanded force field, and python bindings. *Journal of chemical information and modeling*, 2021. 61(8): p. 3891-3898.
- [15] Trott, O. and A.J. Olson, AutoDock Vina: improving the speed and accuracy of docking with a new scoring function, efficient optimization, and multithreading. *Journal of computational chemistry*, 2010. 31(2): p. 455-461.
- [16] Jensen, F., *Introduction to computational chemistry*. 2017: John wiley & sons.
- [17] Hargittai, M., *Stereochemical Applications of Gas-Phase Electron Diffraction, Part A*. 1988: John Wiley & Sons.

- [18] Parr, R.G. Density functional theory of atoms and molecules. in Horizons of Quantum Chemistry: Proceedings of the Third International Congress of Quantum Chemistry Held at Kyoto, Japan, October 29-November 3, 1979. 1989. Springer.
- [19] Fleming, I., Molecular orbitals and organic chemical reactions. 2011: John Wiley & Sons.
- [20] Sheela, N., R. Sebastian, and J. Udaya Prakash, Potential impacts of solvents topological aspects, Vanderwal effect, spectral investigation, and biological features of dodecyl 3, 4, 5-trihydroxybenzoate: anti-viral agent. Spectroscopy Letters, 2025. 58(7): p. 651-666.
- [21] Carreño, A., et al., Study of the structure–bioactivity relationship of three new pyridine Schiff bases: synthesis, spectral characterization, DFT calculations and biological assays. New Journal of Chemistry, 2018. 42(11): p. 8851-8863.
- [22] Neog, B., S. Sinha, and P.K. Bhattacharyya, Alkylation of DNA by nitrogen mustards: A DFT study. Computational and Theoretical Chemistry, 2013. 1018: p. 19-25.
- [23] Ates, T., et al., Comprehensive structural characterization of chromium-doped zinc oxides. Rendiconti Lincei. Scienze Fisiche e Naturali, 2025: p. 1-10.
- [24] Toriyama, M.Y., et al., How to analyse a density of states. Materials Today Electronics, 2022. 1: p. 100002.
- [25] Murray, J.S. and P. Politzer, The electrostatic potential: an overview. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Molecular Science, 2011. 1(2): p. 153-163.
- [26] Kareem, R.O., et al., Epinephrine compound: unveiling its optical and thermochemical properties via quantum computation methods. Chemical Review and Letters, 2023. 6(4): p. 415-427.
- [27] Normanno, N., et al., Epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) signaling in cancer. Gene, 2006. 366(1): p. 2-16.
- [28] Lynch, T.J., et al., Activating mutations in the epidermal growth factor receptor underlying responsiveness of non–small-cell lung cancer to gefitinib. New England Journal of Medicine, 2004. 350(21): p. 2129-2139.